

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1020652>

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:9CCD95EE-18C8-4EF7-A580-26FAA25C1A60

***Strauzia longipennis* (Diptera: Tephritidae), a North American adventive pest of sunflower: current distribution in Europe**

E. P. Kameneva*^{1,2}, S. V. Korneyev**^{1,3}

¹I. I. Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology, NAS of Ukraine, Bogdan Chmielnicki St., 15/2, 01054 Kyiv, Ukraine

²Museum für Naturkunde Berlin, Invalidenstr. 43, 10115 Berlin, Germany

³Plant Pest Diagnostics Center, California Department of Food and Agriculture, 3294 Meadowview Road, Sacramento, CA 95832, USA

E-mail: * kameneva.elena@gmail.com, ** s.v.korneyev@gmail.com

* ORCID <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7986-9942>

** ORCID <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8599-7695>

Kameneva, E. P., Korneyev, S. V. *Strauzia longipennis* (Diptera: Tephritidae), a North American adventive pest of sunflower: current distribution in Europe. — A summary of the taxonomic position, pest status and current occurrence of *Strauzia longipennis* (Wiedemann, 1830), a pest of sunflower and Jerusalem artichoke, in Germany.

Key words. Diptera, Tephritidae, American sunflower stem borer, *Strauzia longipennis*, Europe, Germany.

Каменєва Є. П., Корнейєв С. В. *Strauzia longipennis* (Diptera: Tephritidae), північноамериканський адвентивний шкідник соняшнику: сучасне поширення в Європі. — Коротко описано таксономічне положення, фітосанітарний статус та сучасне поширення *Strauzia longipennis* (Wiedemann, 1830), шкідника соняшнику та топінамбура, в Німеччині.

Ключові слова. Diptera, Tephritidae, стебловий соняшниковий мінер, *Strauzia longipennis*, Європа, Німеччина.

Introduction

Until recently, all species of the genus *Strauzia* Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830 were known mainly from the eastern United States and Canada; according to Stoltzfus (1988), the genus included 12 nominal species, but only 10 were included in the list of North American tephritids; all the species whose larval biology is known develop on plants of the tribe Heliantheae of the family Asteraceae (Foote et al., 1993).

Hippee et al. (2021) provided a molecular-based analysis of phylogenetic relationships in the genus *Strauzia*, which revealed 12 well-differentiated clusters, 11 of which correspond to known species (except *S. stoltzfi* Steyskal, 1986 known from the only type specimen unavailable for molecular analysis) and one possibly undescribed cryptic “host race” which may represent an unnamed new species.

These species are either monophagous on *Ageratina altissima* — *S. rugosa* Stoltzfus, 1988, *Ambrosia trifida* — *S. perfecta* (Loew, 1873), *Helianthus giganteus* — *S. gigantei* Steyskal, 1986, *Helianthus grosseserratus* — *S. arcuata* (Loew, 1873), *S. noctipennis* Stoltzfus, 1988, *S. sp.*, *H. tuberosus* — *S. longitudinalis* (Loew, 1873), *Rudbeckia laciniata* — *S. intermedia* (Loew, 1873), *Smallanthus*

vedalia — *S. uvedaliae* Stoltzfus, 1988, and *Verbesina occidentalis* — *S. verbesinae* Steyskal, 1986 or narrow oligophagous species: *S. longipennis* (Wiedemann, 1830) infests *Helianthus annuus* and *H. tuberosus*, and *S. vittigera* (Loew, 1873) — *H. nuttallii*, *H. strumosus*, and *H. tuberosus*; the host plant of *S. stoltzfi* is unknown (Hippee et al., 2021).

According to Hippee et al. (2021), the most widespread American sunflower stem borer *S. longipennis* includes two genetically distant populations, each of which is associated with *Helianthus annuus* (sunflower) and *H. tuberosus* (Jerusalem artichoke) without any evident host preferences. *Strauzia longipennis* is considered to be an important pest of commercially grown sunflowers (Knodel et al., 2015).

Female lays smooth, white, elongated eggs in shaded parts of the plant; the larvae emerge within a week; there are several larvae in the stem, which tunnel up or down, causing soft tissue to be eaten away and rot; development of the three larval instars takes about 6 weeks; when fully developed, the larvae emerge from the stem, leaving a characteristic exit hole; there are usually ten to twenty exit holes evenly distributed along the stem; the larvae leave the plant around mid-August and pupate in the soil;

stem tunnelling by larvae weakens plants and makes them susceptible to wind and disease (Allen et al., 1954; Baufeld et al., 2020). Larvae leave the stems and pupae overwinter in the soil; adults emerge in early to mid June; the sunflower maggot does not usually present a control problem for the grower; damage to leaves and stalk is generally minimal, despite heavy infestations; although a loss of 37% in seed set has been reported, seed yield is usually not affected by infestations of this insect. (Smith, Wukasch, 2004).

Strauzia longipennis in Germany

The species was observed for the first time in the Palearctic Region in 2010 in Germany; two females walked on the leaves, often on lower surface, and oviposited into the stem on a young sunflower plant (*Helianthus annuus*) in a flower bed; photographs were taken and posted on the diptera.info website (Beuk, 2010) and identified by SVK as *Strauzia longipennis* (Wiedemann, 1830) based on photos on the site or sent by e-mail (Brückner & Korneyev, 2010). Followed this publication, intensive survey begun and the plants in this locality were eradicated.

According to Baufeld et al. (2020), *Strauzia longipennis* belongs to the category of non-European tephritid flies, which are regulated as quarantine pests of the EU; the species was included in the EPPO quarantine pest list, but was subsequently removed

In 2012 / 2013, a winter with severe frost led to a significant decline of the outdoor population in Brandenburg, while the population continued to exist in Berlin and surroundings, but no signs of further natural spread have been detected in Brandenburg in the last 10 years; the authors consider the probability of natural spread from the infested area to be low, as the population density in outdoor sunflower fields is very low; no infestations of Jerusalem artichoke are known in Europe.

Current status

Strauzia longipennis (Wiedemann, 1830) (Figs 1–5)

Material examined. Germany, Berlin, Berlin-Neukölln, St. Jacobi-Friedhof cemetery, 52.468608, 13.42509 [see Fig. 5], on *Helianthus annuus* plant, 18.06.2023, 2♂ (E. Kameneva leg.) (S. Korneyev det.).

Figs 1–4. *Strauzia longipennis*: 1–3 — freshly mounted male specimen; 4 — male on the stem of *Helianthus annuus*, in St. Jacobi-Friedhof.

Fig. 5. *Strauzia longipennis* — occurrence in Berlin, based on own photoregistrations (UkrBIN, 2023).

The specimens were traced while walking on the host plant and photographed (Fig. 4). Later, they were collected with sweeping net and aspirator and killed by freezing at -28°C ; one specimen was placed into 95% alcohol and the other pinned and photographed (Figs 1–3). Both specimens are deposited in the Diptera collection of Museum für Naturkunde Berlin (MNKB). Photo-observations are uploaded at UkrBIN (2023).

Pest status in Europe

According to Baufeld et al. (2020), an increase in damage cannot be completely ruled out in the case of widespread passive spread to southern sunflower growing areas. On the basis of this risk analysis, it is assumed that the species could spread to other parts of Germany or to other EU Member States, but once established, no significant damage is expected. Although *S. longipennis* is a non-European species of Tephritidae, it is not classified as a quarantine pest and Article 29 of Regulation (EU) 2016/2031 does not apply to it.

However, as a precautionary measure, it is recommended that infested plant material be destroyed to prevent the spread of the species. According to a preliminary assessment, the pest potential (low to medium) for the southern EU Member States with extensive sunflower production [as well as for Ukraine — SK] is still uncertain due to lack of data (Baufeld et al., 2020).

Acknowledgements

The authors thank Valery A. Korneyev (Schmalhausener Institute of Zoology Kyiv / Museum für Naturkunde Berlin) and Bernhard Schurian (Museum für Naturkunde Berlin) for their assistance with photography and Michael Ristow (Potsdam University, Plant Ecology and Nature Conservation) for his advice on the localities of interest for collecting tephritoid flies in Berlin / Brandenburg.

References

- Allen, W. R., Westdal, P. D., Barrett, C. F., Askew, W. L. 1954. Control of the Sunflower Maggot, *Strauzia longipennis* (Wied.) (Diptera: Trypetidae), with Demeton. *85th Annual Report of the Entomological Society of Ontario*, 53–56.
- Beuk, P. 2010. Diptera.info. Available from: http://diptera.info/forum/viewthread.php?thread_id=30746. (Accessed 20.11.2023)
- Brückner, C., Korneyev, S. V. 2010. *Strauzia longipennis* (Diptera, Tephritidae) an important pest of sunflowers recorded for the first time in the Palearctic region. *Ukrainska Entomofaunistyka* 1 (1) 55–57.
- Baufeld, P. Wilstermann, A., Schrader G. 2020. *Express-PRA for Strauzia longipennis – Occurrence*. Julius Kühn-Institute, Institute for National and International Plant Health: 1–19. Available at https://pflanzengesundheits.julius-kuehn.de/dokumente/upload/Strauzia-longipennis_ExprPRA_v3_en.pdf (accessed on 21.07.2023)
- Footo, R. H., Blanc, F. L., Norrbom, A. L. 1993. *Handbook of the fruit flies (Diptera: Tephritidae) of America North of Mexico*. Comstock Publishing Associates, Ithaca, 1–571/
- Hippee, A. C., Beer, M., Bagley, A. R. K., Condon, M. A., Kitchen, A., Lisowski, E. A., Norrbom, A. L., Forbes A. A. 2021. Host shifting and host sharing in a genus of specialist flies diversifying alongside their sunflower hosts. *Journal of evolutionary biology*, 34(2), 364–379. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jeb.13740>

- Knodel, J. J., Charlet, L. D., Gavloski, J. 2015. *Integrated Pest Management of Sunflower Insect Pests in the Northern Great Plains*. <http://www.ag.ndsu.edu/pubs/plantsci/pests/e1457.pdf> (accessed on 21.07.2023)
- Smith, S., Wukasch, R. T. 2004. Sunflower maggot *Strauzia longipennis* (Diptera: Trypetidae). Guelph: Pest Diagnostic Clinic, University of Guelph. 2 p. Available at <https://web.archive.org/web/20040723054745/http://www.uoguelph.ca/pdc/Factsheets/PDFs/100SunflowerMaggot.pdf> (Accessed 20.11.2023).
- Stoltzfus, W. B. 1988. The taxonomy and biology of *Strauzia* (Diptera: Tephritidae). *Journal of the Iowa Academy of Sciences*, 95, 117–126.
- UkrBIN. 2023. UkrBIN: Ukrainian Biodiversity Information Network [public project & web application]. UkrBIN, Database on Biodiversity Information. Available from: <http://www.ukrbin.com> (Accessed: November 21, 2023).